

S-Graphicable algebras and specific graph families

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Abstract

This paper presents new developments in the relationship between S -graphicable algebras and graphs. Several general algebraic properties of S -graphicable evolution algebras are established, including characterizations of the annihilator, idempotent elements, and evolution subalgebras. It is also shown that S -graphicable algebras are non-solvable, and several results concerning their perfectness are provided. In addition, new families of S -graphicable algebras are introduced, each associated with well-known graph types, and the structural relationships among these families are analyzed, revealing significant algebraic connections. Finally, an algorithmic method is presented to determine whether a given evolution algebra is S -graphicable and, if so, to construct its associated graph.

Key words: Graphicable algebras, Evolution algebras, Graphs, Derived algebra.

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1 Introduction

Discovering new links and relationships between mathematical fields remains one of the most significant and dynamic research areas in Mathematics. Innovative techniques and alternative approaches allow researchers to tackle unsolved problems, achieve groundbreaking results, and refine existing theories. This paper delves into the intersection of Graph Theory and graphicable algebras, a subclass of evolution algebras. Evolution algebras were introduced by Tian and Vojtechovsky in 2006 [25], with foundational concepts established by Tian shortly thereafter [24]. Subsequent research, including works by Casas et al. [6] and others [5, 10], has explored their structural properties, applications in various fields and connections to other mathematical areas.

Algebraically, evolution algebras can be described as Banach non-associative algebras, while from a dynamical perspective, they function as discrete dynamical systems. These structures form bridges between algebra and other fields, such as genetics, stochastic processes, and graph theory [16, 21, 2]. Notably, Tian's work [24] revealed the relationship between evolution algebras, Markov chains and non-Mendelian genetics, with practical applications in modeling genetic inheritance patterns. Additionally, concepts like solvability in evolution algebras is studied in this paper. This notion can be interpreted biologically representing the extinction of primary generators after a finite number of generations.

Graph Theory, a fundamental tool for addressing complex problems in mathematics, has played a pivotal role in studying semisimple algebras [23] and finite-dimensional algebras [20]. Tian's 2008 work [24] established a connection between evolution algebras and graphs, noting their mutual potential for advancing understanding in both domains. Subsequent research, including contributions by Rozikov, Labra, Elduque, Cabrera, and others, has explored these connections in depth. For example, Rozikov and Tian [21] introduced evolution algebras linked to function spaces of finite graphs, while Elduque and Labra [12] used digraphs to study the nil property of evolution algebras. Recent studies have expanded on these foundations, identifying derivations of evolution algebras [8], exploring random walks on graphs [9] and classifying low-dimensional evolution algebras using pseudodigraphs [11].

As a subset of evolution algebras, graphicable algebras hold significant theoretical and practical importance. Tian initially introduced types of graphicable algebras, such as path, cycle, and complete algebras, correlating them to their respective graphs. Núñez, Rodríguez and Villar [18] expanded on this by exploring generalized graphicable algebras associated with complete n -partite, friendship, star, wheel and Petersen graphs. Their work also introduced the concept of S -graphicable algebras [17], providing a systematic framework for studying these structures.

This paper builds on the research initiated in [18] and [17], introducing new families of S -graphicable algebras associated with n -hypercubes, 20-fullerene, platonic solids, Blanuša, and Pappus graphs. Additionally, it examines relationships and subgraphicable algebras within well-known families, determining the types of S -graphicable algebras associated with the studied graph families. Notably, we establish that no S -graphicable algebras are solvable. In this way, the structure of the paper is as follows: Sec-

tion 2 reviews some concepts and notation on both, evolution algebras and Graph Theory. Next, Section 3 recalls the procedure to associate graphicable algebras and graphs. Section 4 is devoted to studying several structural properties of S -graphicable evolution algebras, such as the annihilator, absolutely nilpotent and idempotent elements, and the extension property. We also prove that there are no solvable S -graphicable algebras and study their perfectness. Section 5 introduces specific families of S -graphicable algebras associated with well-known types of graphs, complementing the study previously developed in [18]. Section 6 is devoted to exploring various relationships and S -graphicable subalgebras within these families of graphs. In Section 7, we analyze in detail the perfectness of the S -graphicable algebras associated with these graph families, a study that was not included in [18]. Section 8 presents the implementation of an algorithmic method designed to verify whether a given evolution algebra is S -graphicable and, in such a case, to construct its associated graph. Section 9 illustrates several applications of the results obtained throughout the paper. Finally, conclusions and references are included.

2 Preliminaries

This section is devoted to recall some preliminary notations about graphs and evolution algebras. Concerning the former, the reader can consult [13]. Regarding the latter, [24] is an introductory reference for evolution algebras and a comprehensive historical perspective on the development of Tian's evolution algebras can be found in [7].

2.1 Evolution algebras

Let $\mathcal{E} \equiv (\mathcal{E}, +, \cdot)$ be an algebra over a field \mathbb{K} . The algebra \mathcal{E} will be called n -dimensional *evolution algebra* if we can find a basis $B = \{e_i\}_{i=1}^n$ of \mathcal{E} such that

1. $e_i^2 = \sum_{k=1}^n c_{i,k} e_k, \forall 1 \leq i \leq n$; and
2. $e_i \cdot e_j = 0, \forall 1 \leq i \neq j \leq n$.

Such a basis B is known as a *natural basis* of the evolution algebra \mathcal{E} , $c_{i,j} \in \mathbb{K}$ are called the *structure constants* and $A = (c_{i,j})$ is named as the *structure matrix*.

The *rank of the structure matrix* of \mathcal{E} , denoted by $\text{rank}(A)$, is the usual rank of the matrix A over the field \mathbb{K} . Since the multiplication in an evolution algebra is completely determined by its structure matrix, several structural properties of \mathcal{E} can be studied in terms of $\text{rank}(A)$.

Throughout this paper, we will consider evolution algebras over the complex numbers field with natural basis B (also called set of generators). Evolution algebras are flexible and commutative [25], but they are not associative either power-associative.

Regarding subspaces of evolution algebras, let \mathcal{E} be an evolution algebra and $\mathcal{E}' \subset \mathcal{E}$ subspace of \mathcal{E} . Then, \mathcal{E}' is a subalgebra of \mathcal{E} if it is closed with respect to the second inner law of \mathcal{E} and it is an evolution subalgebra of \mathcal{E} if it is both subalgebra and of evolution, that is, if there exists a natural basis $B' = \{e_i, i \in \Lambda\}$ of \mathcal{E}' , where $\Lambda \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$, such that $e_i \cdot e_j = 0$ if $i \neq j$. It is said that \mathcal{E}' verifies the extension property if a natural basis B' of \mathcal{E}' can be extended to a natural basis B of \mathcal{E} .

Given an evolution algebra \mathcal{E} with a fixed natural basis B , an element $X \in \mathcal{E}$ is said to be *absolute nilpotent* with respect to B if $X^2 = 0$. Similarly, X is called *idempotent* if $X^2 = X$. The set of all absolute nilpotent elements in \mathcal{E} is denoted by $An(\mathcal{E})$.

The *annihilator* of an evolution algebra \mathcal{E} is defined as $Ann(\mathcal{E}) = \{X \in \mathcal{E} \mid X \cdot Y = 0, \forall Y \in \mathcal{E}\}$. Clearly, $Ann(\mathcal{E}) \subset An(\mathcal{E})$.

Given a finite-dimensional evolution algebra \mathcal{E} , its *derived series* is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{E}^{(1)} = \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{E}^{(2)} = \mathcal{E} \cdot \mathcal{E}, \dots, \mathcal{E}^{(k)} = \mathcal{E}^{(k-1)} \cdot \mathcal{E}^{(k-1)}, \dots$$

We say that \mathcal{E} is *solvable* if there exists a positive integer m such that $\mathcal{E}^{(m)} = \{0\}$. If $\mathcal{E}^{(m-1)} \neq \{0\}$ is also verified, then m is known as the *solvability index* or *solvindex* of \mathcal{E} and it is said that \mathcal{E} is $(m - 1)$ -step solvable.

The derived algebra of an evolution algebra \mathcal{E} will be denoted by $D\mathcal{E} = \mathcal{E}^{(2)}$. An evolution algebra \mathcal{E} is *perfect* if \mathcal{E} and $D\mathcal{E}$ are equal.

In this paper, we will consider a very important subfamily of evolution algebras. These are called *graphicable algebras* and were introduced in 2008 by Tian (see [24]). An n -dimensional graphicable algebra is an evolution algebra where the structure constants $c_{i,j} \in \{0, 1\}, \forall 1 \leq i, j \leq n$ for a natural basis B . Obviously, every graphicable algebra is also an evolution algebra, but the converse is not true in general.

Example 1. The evolution algebra \mathcal{E} with natural basis $\{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$ and products

$$e_1^2 = e_1 + e_2 + e_3, \quad e_2^2 = 2e_1 + e_3, \quad e_3^2 = e_3$$

is not a graphicable algebra.

2.2 Graph Theory

A *graph* is defined as a pair $G = (V, E)$, where V is a non-empty set known as the vertex-set (or node-set) and E is called the edge-set, which is determined by unordered pairs of elements from V . The *order* of a graph G , denoted by $|V|$, is the number of its vertices, while the *size* of G , denoted by $|E|$, is the number of its edges.

A pair of vertices in a graph G are *adjacent or neighbours* if they determine an edge on G . The neighbours of a vertex v are all the vertices which are adjacent to v in G , and this set is known as the *neighbourhood* of v . The *adjacency matrix* of G is the matrix $A = (a_{ij})$, where $a_{i,j} = 1$ if v_i and v_j are adjacent and $a_{i,j} = 0$ otherwise.

The number of vertices adjacent to a vertex v is known as the *degree* of v . The degree of a graph G is given by the minimal degree of all its vertices. Graphs where all the vertices have the same degree are known as *regular graphs*. One special family of regular graphs are *cubic graphs*, that is, regular graphs with degree three.

A *subgraph* of a graph $G = (V, E)$ is a graph $H = (V_H, E_H)$ such that $V_H \subseteq V$ and $E_H \subseteq E$. A particularly relevant case is that of an *induced subgraph*, which contains all the edges of G that connect pairs of vertices in V_H . That is, H is the induced subgraph of G on V_H if for every pair $u, v \in V_H$, the edge $\{u, v\}$ belongs to E_H if and only if it belongs to E . An induced subgraph H of G is said to be *self-contained* if every vertex in V_H has all of its neighbours (in G) also in V_H . In other words, the neighbourhood of each vertex of H is entirely contained within H . This property plays a key role when identifying evolution subalgebras in the context of graphicable evolution algebras.

A *path* in a graph G is a sequence of distinct vertices (v_1, \dots, v_k) such that each pair $\{v_i, v_{i+1}\}$ is an edge of G . A graph is *connected* if there exists a path between any pair of vertices. A *cycle* in a graph is a path (v_1, \dots, v_k) with $k \geq 3$ such that $v_1 = v_k$. A *tree* is a connected graph without cycles.

A *Schlegel diagram* is a projection of a d -dimensional polytope from \mathbb{R}^d to \mathbb{R}^{d-1} through a point just outside one of its facets. This construction was

introduced by Victor Schlegel in 1886 for studying combinatorial and topological properties of polytopes [22]. More precisely, given a convex polytope $P \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, one chooses a facet F of P and a point p just outside F . The central projection of P from p onto the affine space of F produces a $(d-1)$ -dimensional representation of P , called its Schlegel diagram. This diagram preserves the adjacency relations between the vertices and edges of P , so it can be regarded as a graph. For example, the Schlegel diagram of a three-dimensional cube (a polytope in \mathbb{R}^3) is a square with another smaller square inside it, where corresponding vertices are joined (see Figure 1). In general, Schlegel diagrams allow us to represent higher-dimensional polytopes as graphs in lower dimensions, making them a useful tool to introduce several graph families in Section 5.

Figure 1: Cube and its Schlegel diagram.

After these general concepts, we now introduce several well-known families of graphs that will be dealt with in Sections 6 and 7.

A *complete graph* is a graph in which each pair of vertices is connected by an edge. The complete graph with n vertices is usually denoted by K_n . They are regular graphs with degree $n-1$.

A *wheel graph* of n vertices, W_n , is a graph that contains a cycle of length $n-1$ together with an additional central vertex that is adjacent to every vertex of the cycle.

A *complete n -partite graph*, $K_{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n}$, is a graph where the vertex set can be decomposed into n disjoint subsets V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n with $|V_k| = \alpha_k$ for each $1 \leq k \leq n$. No two vertices within the same subset are adjacent, while every pair of vertices belonging to different subsets are adjacent. When $n=2$ the resulting graph is called a bipartite graph.

A *friendship graph* is a graph where every pair of vertices has exactly one common neighbour.

A *directed graph* or *digraph* is defined as a pair $D = (V, E)$, where V is the non-empty vertex set and $E \subseteq V \times V$ is a set of ordered pairs of

vertices, called directed edges or arcs. If $(u, v) \in E$, we say that there is an arc from u to v , and u is called the tail while v is the head of the arc. The notions of adjacency, degree, subgraph and regularity can be extended in a natural way to the directed case by distinguishing between *in-degree* (number of incoming arcs to a vertex) and *out-degree* (number of outgoing arcs from a vertex).

Remark 1. *All the graphs considered in this work are finite. Therefore, whenever the notion of a self-contained subgraph is used, it refers to the union of connected components of the graph, rather than to the proper isomorphic subgraphs considered in the infinite case.*

3 Associating graphicable algebras and graphs

In this section, we examine the association between graphicable algebras and graphs, highlighting foundational definitions and key contributions in the literature. Several works have explored this connection in depth, beginning with the pioneering contributions of Tian in [24], who introduced a procedure to associate an evolution algebra with a graph as follows:

Definition 1. *Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph of order n , where V is the set of vertices and E is the set of edges. Then, G can be associated with a graphicable algebra by taking $V = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$ as the set of generators (natural basis) and considering the following set of relations on the algebra:*

$$e_i^2 = \sum_{e_k \in N(e_i)} e_k; \quad e_i \cdot e_j = 0, \quad i \neq j,$$

where $N(e_i)$ denotes the neighbourhood of e_i .

Conversely, Tian also described how to associate a (possibly directed) graph to a given graphicable algebra. In this construction, the generators of the algebra are taken as the vertices, and a directed edge is drawn from a vertex e_i to each vertex e_k that appears with nonzero coefficient in the expression of e_i^2 .

In the same foundational work, Tian introduced several examples of graphicable algebras, such as cycle algebras, path algebras, and complete algebras, each corresponding to well-known graph families: cycles, paths, and complete graphs, respectively.

Later, Núñez, Rodríguez and Villar extended these ideas in [18], where they investigated generalized graphicable algebras associated with complete

n -partite graphs, star graphs, friendship graphs, wheel graphs, snark graphs, and the Petersen graph. In addition to constructing these families, they analyzed the existence of graphicable subalgebras and introduced the notion of S -graphicable algebras in [17].

An evolution algebra is said to be S -graphicable if it admits a natural basis $B = \{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ such that its structure constants satisfy:

$$c_{i,j} = c_{j,i}, \quad c_{i,i} = 0, \quad \text{for all } i \neq j.$$

This symmetry condition ensures that the associated graph is undirected and simple, making S -graphicable algebras those that correspond precisely to simple graphs via the construction described above.

4 Algebraic properties of S -graphicable algebras and their associated graph

In this section, we establish several structural properties of S -graphicable evolution algebras by analyzing their relation with the associated graphs. We begin by characterizing the annihilator of such an algebra in terms of isolated vertices of the graph, and we prove that the set of absolutely nilpotent elements coincides with the annihilator. We also show that these algebras admit no non-trivial idempotent elements. Furthermore, we investigate the conditions under which a subspace generated by a subset of the natural basis forms an evolution subalgebra, characterizing it in terms of induced subgraphs. As a consequence, we identify a family of evolution subalgebras that satisfy the extension property.

From here on, G will denote the graph associated to an S -graphicable algebra \mathcal{E} and a fixed natural basis $B = \{e_i\}_{i=1}^n$ following the procedure indicated in Section 3.

Proposition 1. *It is verified that*

$$\text{Ann}(\mathcal{E}) = \text{span}\{e_i \mid i \text{ is an isolated vertex}\}$$

Proof. If i is an isolated vertex in G , then there are no edges connecting i to any other vertex. This implies that the structure constants satisfy $c_{i,j} = 0$, for all $1 \leq j \neq i \leq n$, and since $c_{i,i} = 0$, we have $e_i \cdot e_j = 0$, $\forall 1 \leq j \leq n$. Therefore, $e_i \in \text{Ann}(\mathcal{E})$, and by linearity, we get

$$\text{span}\{e_i \mid i \text{ is an isolated vertex in } G\} \subseteq \text{Ann}(\mathcal{E}).$$

Conversely, if $X = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i e_i \in \text{Ann}(\mathcal{E})$, then by the definition of the annihilator we have

$$0 = X \cdot e_j = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i (e_i \cdot e_j) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \left(\sum_{k \in N(i)} c_{i,k} e_k \right), \quad \text{for } 1 \leq j \leq n$$

and where $N(i)$ denotes the set of neighbors of vertex i . Since all structure constants $c_{i,k}$ are non-negative (in our case, 0 or 1), and the field is \mathbb{C} , the above equality can only hold if the coefficients of every e_k vanish. Therefore, for each k ,

$$\sum_{i: k \in N(i)} \lambda_i c_{i,k} = 0.$$

As each term in the sum is non-negative and $c_{i,k} > 0$ whenever i and k are adjacent, this equality implies that $\lambda_i = 0$ for every vertex i having at least one neighbor (i.e., for all non-isolated vertices).

Hence, the only possibly nonzero coefficients correspond to isolated vertices, proving that

$$\text{Ann}(\mathcal{E}) = \text{span}\{e_i \mid i \text{ is an isolated vertex in } G\}.$$

□

Remark 2. *Proposition 1 is not true, in general, for graphicable algebras that are not S -graphicable. For instance, consider the evolution algebra \mathcal{E} with natural basis $\{e_1, e_2\}$ and law $e_1^2 = e_1 + e_2$, $e_2^2 = 0$. The associated graph, G , cannot have isolated vertices. This algebra is graphicable, but not S -graphicable. In this case, $\text{Ann}(\mathcal{E}) = \text{span}\{e_2\}$ and e_2 does not correspond to an isolated vertex in G .*

Proposition 2. *Every absolute nilpotent element of \mathcal{E} corresponds to an isolated vertex of G . Consequently, $\text{Ann}(\mathcal{E}) = \text{An}(\mathcal{E})$.*

Proof. Let \mathcal{E} be an S -graphicable algebra with natural basis $B = \{e_i\}_{i=1}^n$ and we denote by $G = (V, E)$ its associated graph. First, it is obvious that $\text{Ann}(\mathcal{E}) \subset \text{An}(\mathcal{E})$. Let $x = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i e_i$ be an absolute nilpotent element of \mathcal{E} . Then,

$$x^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i^2 e_i^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i^2 \left(\sum_{j=1}^n c_{i,j} e_j \right) = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i^2 c_{i,j} \right) e_j$$

Since \mathcal{E} is an S -graphicable algebra, $c_{i,i} = 0$ and $c_{i,j} \in \{0, 1\}$. Consequently,

$$x^2 = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\sum_{i=1, i \neq j}^n \lambda_i^2 c_{i,j} \right) e_j = 0$$

since x is absolute nilpotent. The previous expression is given by the sum of non-negative terms. We conclude that $x^2 = 0$ implies that all λ_i such that $c_{i,j} = 1$ must vanish. This means that if a vertex j has a neighbor i with $c_{i,j} = 1$, then $\lambda_i = 0$. Applying this to every j , we conclude that x corresponds to an isolated vertex and according to Proposition 1 we have that $x \in \text{Ann}(\mathcal{E})$. □

Proposition 3. *The only idempotent element in \mathcal{E} is the zero element.*

Proof. We denote by $B = \{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ the natural basis of \mathcal{E} . Let $x \in \mathcal{E}$ be an arbitrary element:

$$x = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i e_i, \quad \lambda_i \in \mathbb{K}.$$

Suppose that x is idempotent, i.e., $x^2 = x$. Then,

$$x^2 = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i e_i \right)^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i^2 e_i^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i^2 \sum_{j \neq i} c_{i,j} e_j = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\sum_{i \neq j} \lambda_i^2 c_{i,j} \right) e_j.$$

Imposing $x^2 = x$, we obtain the following system of equations:

$$\sum_{i \neq j} \lambda_i^2 c_{i,j} = \lambda_j, \quad \text{for all } j = 1, \dots, n. \quad (*)$$

Suppose $x \neq 0$, i.e., there exists at least one index k such that $\lambda_k \neq 0$. Let $S = \{i \in \{1, \dots, n\} \mid \lambda_i \neq 0\}$ be the support of x . Fix $j \notin S$. Then, since $\lambda_j = 0$, the equation (*) becomes:

$$\sum_{i \in S} \lambda_i^2 c_{i,j} = 0.$$

But since the coefficients λ_i^2 are nonnegative and at least one is strictly positive, and $c_{i,j} \in \{0, 1\}$, the sum above can only vanish if $c_{i,j} = 0$ for all $i \in S$. That is, j has no neighbors in S .

Therefore, the set S induces a subgraph that is disconnected from the rest of the graph. Since no basis element e_i can satisfy $e_i^2 = e_i$ (due to the absence of loops), and $e_i^2 = 0$ for isolated vertices, it follows that $x^2 = 0$, contradicting the assumption that x is idempotent unless $x = 0$. Thus, the only solution to the system (*) is $\lambda_i = 0$ for all i , i.e., $x = 0$. □

Remark 3. *The hypotheses in Propositions 2 and 3 are essential. In particular, the assumption that the algebra is S -graphicable cannot be removed. The results are not true, in general, for graphicable algebras that are not S -graphicable. Let \mathcal{E} be the evolution algebra with natural basis $\{e_1, e_2\}$ and law $e_1^2 = e_2^2 = e_2$. The associated graph, G , cannot have isolated vertices. This algebra is graphicable, but not S -graphicable. We consider $x = \lambda_1 e_1 + \lambda_2 e_2 \in \mathcal{E}$. Then*

$$x \cdot e_1 = \lambda_1 e_2, \quad x \cdot e_2 = \lambda_2 e_2,$$

so $x \in \text{Ann}(\mathcal{E})$ if and only if $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0$, that is, $\text{Ann}(\mathcal{E}) = \{0\}$. On the other hand,

$$x^2 = (\lambda_1 e_1 + \lambda_2 e_2)^2 = (\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2) e_2,$$

so x is absolutely nilpotent if and only if $\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 = 0$, which has nonzero solutions over \mathbb{C} (e.g., $x = e_1 + i e_2$). Hence, $\text{An}(\mathcal{E}) \neq \text{Ann}(\mathcal{E})$. Moreover, $x = e_2$ is idempotent, as $e_2^2 = e_2$, showing that nontrivial idempotent elements may exist in the non- S -graphicable case.

Proposition 4. *Let $H \subseteq B$ be a subset of basis vectors and $\mathcal{C} = \text{span}(H)$. Then \mathcal{C} is an evolution subalgebra of \mathcal{E} if and only if for every $e_i \in H$, we have $e_i^2 \in \mathcal{C}$. Equivalently, the subgraph of G induced by the vertices corresponding to H is self-contained, i.e., each vertex in H has all its neighbors also in H .*

Proof. Suppose $H = \{e_{i_1}, \dots, e_{i_k}\}$ is a subset of the natural basis of \mathcal{E} , and consider the subspace $\mathcal{C} = \text{span}(H)$. We want to determine when \mathcal{C} is an evolution subalgebra.

Since \mathcal{E} is an evolution algebra, the multiplication of basis elements satisfies:

$$e_i e_j = 0 \quad \text{for } i \neq j, \quad e_i^2 = \sum_{j \neq i} c_{i,j} e_j,$$

with $c_{i,j} \in \{0, 1\}$ and $c_{i,j} = c_{j,i}$.

Let us assume first that $e_i^2 \in \mathcal{C}$ for every $e_i \in H$. Then, since the product of distinct basis elements is zero, the multiplication of any two elements in \mathcal{C} is again a linear combination of elements in H , and hence \mathcal{C} is a subalgebra. Furthermore, the basis H is still orthogonal (products of distinct elements are zero), and each square lies in the span of H , so H is a natural basis for \mathcal{C} and therefore \mathcal{C} is an evolution subalgebra.

Conversely, suppose \mathcal{C} is an evolution subalgebra. Then there exists a natural basis for \mathcal{C} , and in particular, the multiplication of each $e_i \in H$

must satisfy $e_i^2 \in \mathcal{C}$, since otherwise the product would fall outside of \mathcal{C} , contradicting closure under multiplication.

In terms of the graph G associated to \mathcal{E} , the condition $e_i^2 \in \mathcal{C}$ is equivalent to requiring that every neighbor of i in G is also in the set corresponding to H . Hence, H is closed under squaring if and only if H is self-contained.

Therefore, \mathcal{C} is a subalgebra of evolution if and only if $e_i^2 \in \mathcal{C}$ for all $e_i \in H$, completing the proof. \square

Corollary 1. *Let $H \subseteq B$ be a subset such that the induced subgraph on H is self-contained. Then the subspace $\mathcal{C} = \text{span}(H)$ is an evolution subalgebra of \mathcal{E} that satisfies the extension property: the natural basis H can be extended to a natural basis of \mathcal{E} .*

Proof. By the previous proposition, if the induced subgraph on H is self-contained, then for every $e_i \in H$, we have $e_i^2 \in \mathcal{C}$. This means that \mathcal{C} is closed under multiplication and hence an evolution subalgebra of \mathcal{E} .

Moreover, since $H \subseteq B$ and B is a natural basis of \mathcal{E} , we can complete H to a full natural basis of \mathcal{E} by adding elements from $B \setminus H$. The orthogonality is preserved, because the product of distinct basis elements in an evolution algebra is zero. Also, each $e_i \in B \setminus H$ satisfies $e_i^2 \in \text{span}(B)$ by definition of B being a natural basis.

Therefore, the natural basis H of \mathcal{C} can be extended to a natural basis of \mathcal{E} , and \mathcal{C} satisfies the extension property. \square

Example 2. *Let us consider the evolution algebra \mathcal{E} with natural basis $B = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4, e_5\}$ and multiplication given by:*

$$e_1^2 = e_2, \quad e_2^2 = e_1 + e_3, \quad e_3^2 = e_2, \quad e_4^2 = e_5^2 = 0$$

The graph G associated to \mathcal{E} has vertex set $V = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ and edge set $E = \{\{1, 2\}, \{2, 3\}\}$. Thus, the vertices 4 and 5 are isolated.

By Propositions 1 and 2, it is satisfied that

$$\text{An}(\mathcal{E}) = \text{Ann}(\mathcal{E}) = \text{span}\{e_4, e_5\}.$$

Consider the subset $H = \{e_1, e_2, e_3\} \subseteq B$. The induced subgraph on H contains all neighbors of each of its vertices. Therefore, it is self-contained. By Proposition 4 and Corollary 4, the subspace $\mathcal{C} = \text{span}(H) = \text{span}\{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$ is an evolution subalgebra of \mathcal{E} that satisfies the extension property: the natural basis H can be extended to a natural basis of \mathcal{E} by adding e_4 and e_5 .

Now, we study solvability and perfectness of S -graphicable algebras. The following theorem shows that solvability never occurs for this kind of algebras.

Theorem 1. *Let \mathcal{E} be an n -dimensional non-abelian evolution algebra such that there exists a natural basis of \mathcal{E} whose structure constants verify*

$$c_{i,j} = c_{j,i}, \quad c_{i,i} = 0, \quad \forall 1 \leq i \neq j \leq n.$$

Then, \mathcal{E} is non-solvable.

Proof. Let \mathcal{E} be an n -dimensional evolution algebra with natural basis $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^n$ such that

$$e_i^2 = \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n c_{i,j} e_j; \quad e_i \cdot e_j = 0, \quad \forall 1 \leq i \neq j \leq n.$$

Since \mathcal{E} is non-abelian, $\exists 1 \leq i \neq j \leq n$ such that $c_{i,j} \neq 0$. Moreover, we assume that $c_{i,j} = c_{j,i}, \forall 1 \leq i \neq j \leq n$. The derived algebra of \mathcal{E} is given by

$$\mathcal{D}\mathcal{E} = \mathcal{E}^{(2)} = \left\langle \left\{ \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n c_{i,j} e_j \mid c_{i,j} = c_{j,i} \neq 0, 1 \leq i \neq j \leq n \right\} \right\rangle.$$

The structure matrix of \mathcal{E} is

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & c_{1,2} & c_{1,3} & \cdots & \cdots & c_{1,n} \\ c_{1,2} & 0 & c_{2,3} & c_{2,4} & \cdots & c_{2,n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ c_{1,n-1} & c_{2,n-1} & \cdots & c_{n-2,n-1} & 0 & c_{n-1,n} \\ c_{1,n} & c_{2,n} & \cdots & c_{n-2,n} & c_{n-1,n} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

This matrix is symmetric and the elements in its main diagonal are all zero. Under these conditions, it is verified that

$$e_i^2 \cdot e_j^2 = \sum_{k=1, k \neq i,j}^n c_{i,k} c_{j,k} e_k^2.$$

Due to this, $\mathcal{E}^{(3)} = \mathcal{E}^{(2)}$ and, therefore, \mathcal{E} is not solvable. □

Corollary 2. *Every S -graphicable algebra is non-solvable.*

Proof. It follows from adding the condition $c_{i,j} \in \{0, 1\}, \forall 1 \leq i \neq j \leq n$ to Theorem 1 □

In case of perfectness, we have the following results:

Proposition 5. *Let \mathcal{E} be an n -dimensional S -graphicable algebra and let A be the adjacency matrix of the associated graph G . Then \mathcal{E} is perfect if and only if $\text{rank}(A) = n$.*

Proof. By definition $D\mathcal{E} = \text{span}\{e_i^2 : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. Writing each e_i^2 in the basis B the coordinate vectors are precisely the rows of A . Hence $D\mathcal{E}$ corresponds to the row-space of A and $\dim D\mathcal{E} = \text{rank}(A)$. Therefore $D\mathcal{E} = \mathcal{E}$ holds exactly when $\text{rank}(A) = n$. \square

The previous proposition reduces the problem of perfectness to analyzing the adjacency matrix.

Corollary 3. *If the associated graph G has an isolated vertex then \mathcal{E} is not perfect.*

Proof. An isolated vertex gives a zero row in A , so $\text{rank}(A) < n$. \square

Corollary 4. *If G has two distinct vertices with identical neighbourhoods (i.e. two equal rows in A), then \mathcal{E} is not perfect.*

Proof. Equal rows in A make the rows linearly dependent, hence $\text{rank}(A) < n$. \square

5 New families of S -graphicable algebras

The primary objective of this section is to present new advancements related to families of graphs and their associated S -graphicable algebras. We follow a procedure similar to the one outlined in the previous section, addressing the additional challenges posed by families of graphs with a large number of edges and vertices. Specifically, we identify the S -graphicable algebras linked to n -hypercubes, 20-fullerene, platonic solids, Blanuša and Pappus graphs.

The families of graphs considered in this section are classical objects in graph theory and discrete mathematics, with well-established applications in diverse areas. For instance, hypercube graphs play a central role in network design and parallel computing, due to their symmetry and high connectivity [14, 15]. Platonic solid graphs arise naturally in polyhedral theory and geometry and also appear as simplified models in chemistry. Fullerene graphs are directly related to the structure of carbon molecules and are widely studied in mathematical chemistry and nanotechnology [1]. Blanuša graphs, as

classical snarks, provide important counterexamples in extremal graph theory and graph coloring problems [3]. Finally, the Pappus graph is linked to projective geometry through the Pappus configuration [19] and has been extensively investigated in combinatorics. Their high degree of symmetry and structural richness make them especially suitable for exploring the interplay between evolution algebras and families of graphs.

From now on, the algebra law associated with a graph is defined in the usual way: if $B = \{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ is the natural basis, then e_i^2 is the sum of the basis elements corresponding to the neighbors of vertex i . Indices are taken modulo n (the residue), with the convention that index 0 is replaced by n . Once the graph is given, the law of the corresponding S -graphicable algebra is therefore immediate. For illustrative purposes, we write down explicitly the algebra law in a couple of examples (the hypercube Q_4 and the Pappus graph). In the remaining cases, the graph depiction suffices.

5.1 n -hypercube S -graphicable algebras

The n -hypercube graph, denoted by Q_n , is a regular graph of degree n with 2^n vertices and $n2^{n-1}$ edges. This graph can also be constructed by creating a vertex for each n -digit binary number and two vertices would be adjacent if their binary representations differ in a single digit.

Note that Q_1 and Q_2 correspond to the path graphs P_1 and P_2 . More involved cases appear for $n \geq 3$. In particular, Q_3 (the cube graph) will be studied in Subsection 5.3, while the case Q_4 (the 4-dimensional hypercube) is shown in Figure 2 and associated with an S -graphicable algebra below.

Definition 2. *Let $A(Q_4)$ be the S -graphicable algebra associated to the hypercube graph Q_4 . Then, $A(Q_4)$ is called hypercube S -graphicable algebra. If $\{e_1, \dots, e_{16}\}$ is a natural basis for this algebra, its law is given by*

$$\begin{aligned} e_i^2 &= e_{i-1} + e_{i+1} + e_{i+7} + e_{i+9} \pmod{16}, & \text{for } 1 \leq i \leq 8; \\ e_i^2 &= e_{i-9} + e_{i-7} + e_{i+3} + e_{i+5} \pmod{16}, & \text{for } i = 10, 11; \\ e_i^2 &= e_{i-9} + e_{i-7} + e_{i-3} + e_{i+3} \pmod{16}, & \text{for } i = 12, 13; \\ e_i^2 &= e_{i-9} + e_{i-7} + e_{i-5} + e_{i-3} \pmod{16}, & \text{for } i = 14, 15; \\ e_i^2 &= e_{i-7} + e_{i-1} \pmod{8}, +e_{i+3} + e_{i+5} \pmod{16}, & \text{for } i = 9, 16. \end{aligned}$$

5.2 20-Fullerene S -graphicable algebras

In graph theory, fullerene graphs are the Schlegel representations of the corresponding fullerene compounds. The term fullerene refers to any regular

Figure 2: Graph Q_4 .

graph of degree three that is planar with all the faces of size 5 or 6 (including the external face). According to Euler's formula, there will be exactly 12 pentagons in a fullerene. An algorithm to generate all the non-isomorphic fullerenes with a given number of hexagonal faces has been developed by G. Brinkmann and A. Dress [4].

Due to reasons of length we will only study in detail the 20-fullerene (dodecahedral graph). This graph, represented in Figure 3, has 20 vertices, 30 edges and can be associated to an S -graphicable algebra.

5.3 Platonic solid S -graphicable algebras

As it is well-known, the platonic solids are the tetrahedron, cube, octahedron, icosahedron and dodecahedron. They are the only regular convex polyhedra made of regular polygons. The Platonic graphs are the Schlegel diagrams of the five platonic solids.

The tetrahedron graph (see Figure 4) is isomorphic to the wheel graph W_4 and the complete graph K_4 . Wheel graphs were introduced in general in [18, Definition 2.4] and complete graphs in [24].

The cube graph represented in Figure 5 and can be associated with an S -graphicable algebra.

The octahedral graph has 6 vertices and 12 edges with the connectivity of the octahedron. This graph is represented in Figure 6.

Figure 3: Graph 20-fullerene.

Figure 4: Tetrahedron graph.

Figure 5: Graph Q_3 .

Figure 6: Octahedral graph.

The dodecahedral graph is the Platonic graph corresponding to the connectivity of the vertices of a dodecahedron. The dodecahedral graph is a cubic graph having 20 nodes and 30 edges. Figure 7 shows a representation of this graph.

Figure 7: Dodecahedral graph.

The icosahedral graph is the Platonic graph whose nodes have the connectivity of the regular icosahedron. This graph is represented in Figure 8 and has 12 vertices and 30 edges.

5.4 Blanuša S -graphicable algebras

In [18], the authors dealt with Snark S -graphicable algebras. More concretely, they defined Tietze and Flower S -graphicable algebras. In order to complement the previous study, Blanuša S -graphicable algebras are intro-

Figure 8: Icosahedral graph.

duced here. Blanuša snarks are 3-regular graphs with 18 vertices and 27 edges that were discovered by Danilo Blanuša in 1946 [3] when the Petersen graph was the unique snark known. A Blanuša snark is represented in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Blanuša snark graph.

5.5 Pappus S -graphicable algebras

In [18], the authors dealt with S -graphicable algebras associated with generalized Petersen graphs. More concretely, they defined Dürer, Möbius-Kantor, Desargues and Nauru S -graphicable algebras. In order to complement the previous study, Pappus S -graphicable algebras are introduced

here. Pappus graph, represented in Figure 10, is a bipartite, 3-regular graph with 18 vertices and 27 edges formed as the Levi graph of the Pappus configuration. It was named after Pappus of Alexandria, an ancient Greek mathematician who is believed to have discovered the “hexagon theorem” describing the Pappus configuration.

Figure 10: Pappus graph.

Definition 3. Let $A(P)$ be the S -graphicable algebra associated to the Pappus graph P . Then $A(P)$ is called Pappus S -graphicable algebra. Let $\{e_1, \dots, e_{18}\}$ be a natural basis for this algebra. Then, the products are

$$\begin{aligned} e_i^2 &= e_{i+1} + e_{i+7} + e_{i+17} \pmod{18}, & \text{for } i = 1, 3, 7, 9, 13, 15; \\ e_i^2 &= e_{i-1} + e_{i+1} + e_{i+11} \pmod{18}, & \text{for } i = 2, 4, 8, 10, 14, 16; \\ e_i^2 &= e_{i-1} + e_{i+1} + e_{i+13} \pmod{18}, & \text{for } i = 5, 11, 17; \\ e_i^2 &= e_{i-1} + e_{i+1} + e_{i+5} \pmod{18}, & \text{for } i = 6, 12, 18. \end{aligned}$$

6 Relationships between several families

In this section, we show several relationships among some of the previous families of S -graphicable algebras. We will deal with path, cycle, complete, wheel, stars and friendship graphs considering the notation and vertex labels used in [18].

Since many of these graphs are related by inclusion (one being a subgraph of another), it is convenient to first establish a general result that allows us to construct the algebra associated with a graph from that of one of its subgraphs.

Lemma 1. *Let G be a graph and H a subgraph of G . Denote by $A(H)$ and $A(G)$ the corresponding S -graphicable algebras. Then, $A(G)$ can be obtained from $A(H)$ by adding to the square of each generator e_i the basis elements associated to the vertices adjacent to i in G but not in H .*

Proof. By definition, in an S -graphicable algebra associated to a graph $G = (V, E)$ with natural basis $\{e_i\}_{i \in V}$, we have

$$e_i^2 = \sum_{j \in N_G(i)} e_j,$$

where $N_G(i)$ is the set of neighbors of vertex i in G . If H is a subgraph of G , then $N_H(i) \subseteq N_G(i)$ for all i . Therefore,

$$e_i^2|_{A(G)} = e_i^2|_{A(H)} + \sum_{j \in N_G(i) \setminus N_H(i)} e_j.$$

This proves the claim. □

According to Lemma 1, we have the following remarks:

Remark 4. *Let $A(P_n)$ and $A(C_n)$ be the S -graphicable algebras associated to a path and a cycle graph with n vertices, respectively. Then, $A(C_n)$ can be obtained from $A(P_n)$ by adding to this latter the term e_n in e_1^2 and also e_1 in e_n^2 .*

Remark 5. *The complete S -graphicable algebra $A(K_n)$ can be obtained from the cycle algebra $A(C_n)$ by adding to e_i^2 the terms corresponding to the additional neighbors in K_n , that is,*

$$\{e_{i+2}, e_{i+3}, \dots, e_{i+n-2} \pmod{n}\}.$$

Remark 6. *Let $A(K_n)$ and $A(W_n)$ denote the S -graphicable algebras associated to the complete and the wheel graphs, respectively. Observe that W_n can be obtained from C_{n-1} by adding a central vertex connected to all others. Therefore, $A(W_n)$ can be constructed from $A(C_{n-1})$ by adding a new generator e_n such that*

$$e_n^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} e_i,$$

and modifying the squares of the previous generators as

$$e_i^2|_{A(W_n)} = e_i^2|_{A(C_{n-1})} + e_n, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n-1.$$

Remark 7. Let $A(W_n)$ and $A(S_n)$ be the S -graphicable algebras associated to the wheel and the star graphs with n vertices, respectively. Since S_n can be viewed as a subgraph of W_n obtained by removing the outer cycle edges, the algebra $A(S_n)$ is obtained from $A(W_n)$ by eliminating, in each e_i^2 for $1 \leq i \leq n-1$, the terms corresponding to the neighbors along the cycle, keeping only the connection with the central vertex:

$$e_i^2|_{A(S_n)} = e_n, \quad \text{and} \quad e_n^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} e_i.$$

Remark 8. Let $A(S_n)$ and $A(F_n)$ be the S -graphicable algebras associated to the star and friendship graphs, respectively. The friendship graph F_n can be constructed by joining n triangles at a common vertex. In algebraic terms, $A(F_n)$ can be obtained from $A(S_{2n+1})$ by adding, for each pair of leaves (e_{2i-1}, e_{2i}) , an edge between them, which in the algebraic structure corresponds to the addition of the terms e_{2i} in e_{2i-1}^2 and e_{2i-1} in e_{2i}^2 :

$$e_{2i-1}^2 = e_{2i} + e_{2n+1}, \quad e_{2i}^2 = e_{2i-1} + e_{2n+1}, \quad \text{for } 1 \leq i \leq n,$$

and

$$e_{2n+1}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{2n} e_i.$$

7 Perfectness of S -graphicable algebras associated with specific graph families

In this section, we develop a study about the perfectness of the S -graphicable algebras associated with all the different families of graphs considered in this current paper and also some from [18].

Proposition 6. *The S -graphicable path algebra with n vertices, $A(P_n)$, is perfect if and only if n is even.*

Proof. Let us suppose that $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^n$ is a natural basis of $A(P_n)$. First, if n is odd, then $n = 2k + 1$. The products for this algebra are given by

$$e_1^2 = e_2; \quad e_n^2 = e_{n-1}; \quad e_i^2 = e_{i+1} + e_{i-1}, \quad \forall 1 < i < n.$$

Therefore, it is verified that

$$A(P_n)^{(2)} = \text{span} \left(\{e_{2j+1}^2\}_{j=0}^k \right) = \text{span} \left(\{e_{2j}, e_{2j-1} + e_{2j+1}\}_{j=1}^k \right).$$

Consequently, $A(P_n)$ is non-perfect since $\dim(A(P_n)^{(2)}) = 2k < n$. Now, we suppose that n is even. Then, $n = 2k$. In this case,

$$\begin{aligned} A(P_n)^{(2)} &= \text{span}\left(\{e_i^2\}_{i=1}^{2k}\right) = \text{span}\left(e_2, \{e_{2j} + e_{2j+2}\}_{j=1}^{k-1}\right) \cup \\ &\quad \text{span}\left(\{e_{2j-1} + e_{2j+1}\}_{j=1}^{k-1}, e_{2k-1}\right) = \\ &\quad \text{span}\{e_2, e_4, \dots, e_{2k}\} \cup \text{span}\{e_1, e_3, \dots, e_{2k-1}\} = \text{span}\left(\{e_i\}_{i=1}^{2k}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, $A(P_n)^{(2)} = A(P_n)$ and $A(P_n)$ is a perfect S -graphicable algebra. \square

Proposition 7. *The S -graphicable complete algebra with n vertices, $A(K_n)$, is perfect.*

Proof. The adjacency matrix of $A(K_n)$ is $J - I$ (where J is the all-ones matrix and I is the identity matrix). Its eigenvalues are $n - 1$ (simple) and -1 (multiplicity $n - 1$), so $\det(J - I) \neq 0$ and $\text{rank}(J - I) = n$. Consequently, $A(K_n)$ is perfect according to Proposition 5. \square

Proposition 8. *The S -graphicable cycle algebra with n vertices ($n \geq 3$), $A(C_n)$, is perfect if and only if $n \neq 4$.*

Proof. First, if $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^n$ is a list of generators of $A(C_n)$, then its products are

$$e_i^2 = e_{i+1} + e_{i+n-1} \pmod{n}, \text{ for } i = 1, n;$$

$$e_i^2 = e_{i+1} + e_{i+n-1}, \forall 1 < i < n.$$

The graph C_3 is indeed the complete graph K_3 which is perfect due to Proposition 7. For $n \geq 5$, the structure matrix of $A(C_n)$ has rank n . Therefore, $A(C_n)$ is perfect according to Proposition 5. In case that $n = 4$, $A(C_4)$ verifies that $e_1^2 = e_3^2 = e_2 + e_4$ and $e_2^2 = e_4^2 = e_1 + e_3$. Therefore, $A(C_4)^{(k)} = \text{span}\{e_1^2, e_2^2\}$, $\forall k \geq 2$ and $A(C_4)$ is not perfect. \square

Proposition 9. *The complete n -partite S -graphicable algebra $A(K_{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n})$ with $\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \dots + \alpha_n$ vertices is not perfect.*

Proof. The complete n -partite graph $K_{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n}$ has a vertex set, which is given by $V = V_1 \cup V_2 \cup \dots \cup V_n$, where $V_1 = \{1, \dots, \alpha_1\}$, $V_2 = \{\alpha_1 + 1, \dots, \alpha_1 + \alpha_2\}$, \dots , $V_n = \{\alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_{n-1} + 1, \dots, \alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_n\}$. All the vertices in every vertex set V_i for $1 \leq i \leq n$ have the same neighbours. Therefore, $A(K_{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n})$ is not perfect according to Corollary 4. \square

Complete n -partite graphs were defined in [18, Definition 2.1], but there is a mistake on the law concerning the upper index of the summatory in the expression of e_i^2 when $a_1 + a_2 < i \leq a_1 + a_2 + a_3$. Due to this fact, the law of this type of graphs is shown in the following

Remark 9. *The complete n -partite S -graphicable algebra has set of generators $\{e_1, \dots, e_{\alpha_1}, \dots, e_{\alpha_1+\alpha_2}, \dots, e_{\alpha_1+\dots+\alpha_n}\}$ and law*

$$\begin{aligned}
e_i^2 &= \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha_2+\dots+\alpha_n} e_{\alpha_1+k}, & \text{for } 1 \leq i \leq \alpha_1; \\
e_i^2 &= \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha_1} e_k + \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha_3+\dots+\alpha_n} e_{k+\alpha_1+\alpha_2}, & \text{for } \alpha_1 < i \leq \alpha_1 + \alpha_2; \\
e_i^2 &= \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha_1+\alpha_2} e_k + \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha_4+\dots+\alpha_n} e_{k+\alpha_1+\alpha_2+\alpha_3}, & \text{for } \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 < i \leq \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3; \\
&\vdots & \vdots \\
e_i^2 &= \sum_{k=1}^{\alpha_1+\dots+\alpha_{n-1}} e_k, & \text{for } \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \alpha_j < i \leq \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_j.
\end{aligned}$$

Corollary 5. *The S -graphicable complete bipartite algebra with $n + m$ vertices, $A(K_{n,m})$, is not perfect.*

Proof. This follows from the fact that $K_{n,m}$ are a specific case of Proposition 9. □

Corollary 6. *The S -graphicable star algebra, $A(S_n)$, is not perfect.*

Proof. This follows from the fact that $S_n = K_{1,n}$. □

Proposition 10. *The S -graphicable friendship algebra with $2n + 1$ vertices, $A(F_n)$, is perfect.*

Proof. Let $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^{2n+1}$ be a natural basis for $A(F_n)$. The law of this algebra is given by

$$\text{For } 1 \leq i \leq 2n, \quad e_i^2 = \begin{cases} e_{i+1} + e_{2n+1} & \text{if } i \text{ is even,} \\ e_{i-1} + e_{2n+1} & \text{if } i \text{ is odd.} \end{cases}; \quad e_{2n+1}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{2n} e_i;$$

where $2n + 1$ is the common vertex to the remaining ones in F_n . The structure

matrix of $A(F_n)$ is

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & \cdots & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The rank of this matrix is maximum and therefore $A(F_n)$ is perfect according to Proposition 5. \square

Proposition 11. *The S -graphicable wheel algebra with n vertices, $A(W_n)$, is perfect if and only if $n \neq 5$.*

Proof. It suffices to bear in mind the definition of W_n and Proposition 8. \square

Proposition 12. *The S -graphicable algebras $A(T)$, $A(Q_3)$ and $A(I)$ are perfect.*

Proof. Let us consider the cube S -graphicable algebra, $A(Q_3)$. This algebra has as natural basis $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^8$ and structure matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

It is easy to prove that this matrix has maximal rank. Consequently, $A(Q_3)$ is perfect according to Proposition 5. \square

8 Algorithmic method

In this section, we present an algorithmic approach to determine whether a given evolution algebra is S -graphicable. If so, we provide the representation of its associated graph. The implementation has been carried out using the symbolic computation package Maple (version 12 or higher). For

this purpose, we utilized the libraries `LinearAlgebra`, `GraphTheory`, and `ListTools`, which provide commands related to graph theory, linear algebra, and list manipulation.

This computational approach complements the theoretical results obtained in the previous sections, providing a practical tool to check whether a given evolution algebra satisfies the S -graphicability conditions and to visualize its associated graph. The procedure also serves to support the examples and applications described in Section 9.

Following the previously established notation, let \mathcal{E} be an evolution algebra of dimension n , and let B denote its natural basis. The algorithm is outlined in the following steps:

1. Introducing the products of the evolution algebra \mathcal{E} .

The implementation of this step is managed by the subprocedure `prod`. This subprocedure takes as input the subindex i of a basis vector in B and returns the product e_i^2 . Conditional statements are required to handle each non-zero product. Since the subprocedure needs to be completed by the user according to the multiplication law of \mathcal{E} , an initial statement is included to remind the user of this requirement. Additionally, it is necessary to clear any previous calculations and reset the variables before assigning a value to `dim`, which stores the dimension of \mathcal{E} .

```
> restart: with(LinearAlgebra): with(GraphTheory): with(ListTools):
> assign(dim,...):
> prod:=proc(i)
>   if i=... then ...;
>   elif ... then ...;
>   ...
>   elif ... then ...;
>   else 0; fi;
> end proc;
```

The ellipsis in command `assign` are for $dim(\mathcal{E})$. The other suspension points correspond to the introduction of the non-zero products of \mathcal{E} and conditional sentences for them.

2. Checking if the given evolution algebra \mathcal{E} is S -graphicable.

This step is dedicated to verifying whether the given evolution algebra \mathcal{E} , whose multiplication law was defined in the previous step, is

S -graphicable. This means that we analyze whether \mathcal{E} can be represented by a simple graph. To achieve this, we implement the subroutine `Sgraphicable`. This subroutine takes as input the dimension n of \mathcal{E} and returns one of two messages: “The algebra is S -graphicable” if \mathcal{E} satisfies the necessary conditions, or “The algebra is not S -graphicable” otherwise. For the implementation, we define a local variable L , which stores the structure constants $c_{i,i}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $c_{i,j} - c_{j,i}$ for $1 \leq i < j \leq n$. If all these constants are zero, then \mathcal{E} is determined to be S -graphicable.

```

>Sgraphicable:=proc(n)
> local L;
> L:=[];
> for i from 1 to n do
>   L:=[op(L),coeff(prod(i),e[i])];
>   for j from i+1 to n do
>     L:=[op(L),coeff(prod(i),e[j])-coeff(prod(j),e[i])];
>   od;
> od;
> L:=MakeUnique(L);
> if L=[0] then print(The algebra is S-graphicable)
>   else print(The algebra is not S-graphicable)
> fi;
> end proc:

```

3. Obtaining the graph associated with \mathcal{E} .

It is important to note that this step is performed only if the output of the previous step confirms the S -graphicable nature of the algebra. In such a case, the subprocedure `drawinggraph` is executed. This subprocedure takes as its sole input the dimension n of the S -graphicable algebra \mathcal{E} and generates a visual representation of its associated graph. To achieve this, two local variables are defined: E and V . The list E is constructed from the edges of the graph, while V represents the list of vertices determined by the value of `dim`. The implementation involves evaluating and analyzing the structure constants of the algebra to accurately determine the graph’s edges and vertices.

```

>drawinggraph:=proc(n)
> local V,E;
> V:=[seq(i,i=1..n)];
> E:={};

```

```

> for i from 1 to n do
>   if prod(i)<>0 then
>     for j from 1 to n do
>       if j<>i then
>         if coeff(prod(i),e[j])<>0 then
>           E:={op(E),{i,j}};
>           fi;
>           fi;
>         od;
>       fi;
>     od;
> DrawGraph(Graph(V,E));
> end proc:

```

Example 3. Now, we consider the following example of an evolution algebra \mathcal{E} with dimension 5, natural basis $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^5$ and law

$$e_1^2 = 2e_2 + e_3, \quad e_3^2 = 2e_1 - e_3 + 2e_5, \quad e_4^2 = e_1, \quad e_5^2 = 3e_2 - e_3.$$

First, one has to fill in the implementation of the subroutine `prod`:

```

> if i=1 then 2*e[2]+e[3];
> elif i=3 then 2*e[1]-e[3]+2*e[5];
> elif i=4 then e[1];
> elif i=5 then 3*e[2]-e[3];
> else 0; fi;

```

Next, the subprocedure `Sgraphicable` must be executed obtaining:

```

> Sgraphicable(dim);
The algebra is not S-graphicable.

```

This is due to the fact that the variable `L` in the implementation of this subroutine is given by

```

> L=[0,2,-1,-3,3]

```

Since \mathcal{E} is not *S-graphicable*, we will not evaluate the last routine.

Example 4. Let us consider the graphicable algebra \mathcal{E} with dimension 5, natural basis $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^5$ and law

$$e_1^2 = e_3 + e_4, \quad e_3^2 = e_1 + e_5, \quad e_4^2 = e_1, \quad e_5^2 = e_3.$$

First, one has to fill in the implementation of the subroutine `prod`:

```

> if i=1 then e[3]+e[4];
> elif i=2 then e[4]+e[5];
> elif i=3 then e[1]+e[5];
> elif i=4 then e[1]+e[2];
> elif i=5 then e[2]+e[3];
> else 0; fi;

```

Next, the subprocedure `Sgraphicable` must be executed obtaining:

```

> Sgraphicable(dim);
The algebra is S-graphicable.

```

Finally, we evaluate the main procedure `drawingraph` obtaining the graph of Figure 11.

```

> drawingraph(dim);

```


Figure 11: Graph associated to a 5-dimensional S -graphicable algebra.

Finally, the complexity of the procedure is computed bearing in mind the number of calculation executed in the worst case. For this purpose, we use the notation based on the big O (see [26]). In this way, fixed $f, g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $f(x) = O(g(x)) \Leftrightarrow \exists M \in \mathbb{R}, M > 0$ and $\exists x' \in \mathbb{R}$ verifying that $|f(x)| \leq M \cdot g(x), \forall x \geq x'$.

Let $N_i(n)$ be the number of operations carried out in the Step i . This function depends on the dimension n of the evolution algebra. In Table 1, we can see the number of operations and the complexity order of every step.

Step	Procedure	Complexity	Number of Operations
1	prod	$O(n^2)$	$N_1(n) = 1 + \frac{n(n-1)}{2}$
2	Sgraphicable	$O(n^4)$	$N_2(n) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n N_1(n)$
3	drawingraph	$O(n^4)$	$N_3(n) = 3 + \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n N_1(n)$

Table 1: Number of operations and complexity order of each step.

9 Applications

In this section, we illustrate how the algorithmic procedure developed in Section 8 can be applied to analyze specific examples of S -graphicable algebras. These cases show how the structural results obtained in Section 7 can be effectively used to determine properties such as perfectness directly from the associated graph, without computing the derived series explicitly.

Example 5. Let \mathcal{E} be the graphicable algebra with natural basis $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^9$ and multiplication given by:

$$e_1^2 = \sum_{j=2}^9 e_j, \quad e_2^2 = e_1 + e_3, \quad e_3^2 = e_1 + e_2, \quad e_4^2 = e_1 + e_5,$$

$$e_5^2 = e_1 + e_4, \quad e_6^2 = e_1 + e_7, \quad e_7^2 = e_1 + e_6, \quad e_8^2 = e_1 + e_9, \quad e_9^2 = e_1 + e_8.$$

Using the algorithmic procedures in Section 8, we verify that this is an S -graphicable algebra and its associated graph is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Graph associated to graphicable algebra \mathcal{E} .

The graph corresponds to the friendship graph F_4 . By Proposition 10, we conclude that \mathcal{E} is a perfect S -graphicable algebra.

Another application of the results in Section 7 is the identification of perfect evolution subalgebras within a decomposable S -graphicable algebra. This offers a deeper understanding of the internal structure of the algebra: perfect subalgebras may reveal symmetries or intrinsic properties not immediately visible. In addition, such subalgebras tend to be more manageable, enabling simplified computations or theoretical developments. Their study can also provide insights into the dynamics modeled by the evolution algebra, with potential applications in fields such as biology, physics, and network science.

Example 6. Let \mathcal{E} be the graphicable algebra with natural basis $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^8$ and multiplication rules:

$$\begin{aligned} e_1^2 &= e_2, & e_2^2 &= e_1 + e_3, & e_3^2 &= e_2 + e_4, & e_4^2 &= e_3, \\ e_5^2 &= e_6 + e_7 + e_8, & e_6^2 &= e_5 + e_7 + e_8, & e_7^2 &= e_5 + e_6 + e_8, & e_8^2 &= e_5 + e_6 + e_7. \end{aligned}$$

According to the methods in Section 8, this algebra is S -graphicable, and its associated graph is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Graph associated to graphicable algebra \mathcal{E} .

The graph consists of two connected components: a path graph P_4 and a complete graph K_4 . According to Propositions 6 and 7, the subalgebras generated by $\{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4\}$ and by $\{e_5, e_6, e_7, e_8\}$ are perfect. Hence, \mathcal{E} admits two perfect evolution subalgebras.

These examples also connect with the notion of self-contained induced subgraphs, that is, induced subgraphs where every neighbor of each vertex

in the subgraph also lies within the subgraph. As shown in Section 4, a subspace generated by a subset of the natural basis forms an evolution subalgebra if and only if the corresponding set of vertices defines a self-contained induced subgraph.

When this condition holds and the original algebra is S -graphicable, the resulting evolution subalgebra inherits graphicability and satisfies the extension property: its natural basis can be extended to a natural basis of the whole algebra. This property is particularly useful for constructing or decomposing evolution algebras while preserving control over the graph-theoretic structure. The identification of such subalgebras thus becomes an effective tool for studying decomposability, ideal structure, and other internal features of evolution algebras arising from graphs.

10 Conclusions and future directions

This manuscript establishes a strong connection between graphicable evolution algebras and graph theory, contributing both theoretical insights and concrete constructions. In particular, Section 4 provides a detailed structural analysis of S -graphicable evolution algebras, including a full characterization of the annihilator and the set of absolutely nilpotent elements, as well as necessary and sufficient conditions for the existence of evolution subalgebras based on induced subgraphs. These results reinforce the correspondence between algebraic properties and graph-theoretic structures, especially in the presence of isolated vertices.

In addition, several new families of S -graphicable algebras associated with well-known graph types such as n -hypercubes, Platonic solids, 20-fullerene graphs, Blanuša snarks and the Pappus graph have been introduced and analyzed. We have proved that no S -graphicable algebra is solvable and studied the perfectness of the algebras associated with these families. Furthermore, subgraphicable relationships among some families have been investigated, and a classification of the algebraic types arising from these and other families in [18] has been completed.

To support the theoretical framework, we have also introduced an algorithmic method for determining whether a given evolution algebra is S -graphicable, offering a computational complement to the structural results.

From the author's perspective, the tools, concepts, and findings presented in this work may prove useful for further developing the interface between evolution algebras and graph theory. Several directions for future

research remain open, including:

1. Analyzing whether the structural results obtained for S -graphicable algebras can be extended to general graphicable algebras.
2. Using S -graphicable algebras such as $A(P_n)$, $A(C_n)$, $A(F_n)$, $A(K_n)$, $A(W_n)$, $A(T)$, $A(Q_3)$, and $A(I)$ to compute perfect evolution subalgebras.
3. Introducing new graph-based notions in this context, such as planar graphicable algebras.
4. Studying the behavior of graphicable algebras under standard graph operations such as union, intersection, join, and various graph products.
5. Translating classical graph-theoretic concepts such as colorability and connectivity into the language of graphicable algebras.

These directions aim to deepen the algebraic understanding of graphic structures and expand the reach of evolution algebras in combinatorial and applied contexts.

Declarations

The author has no conflict of interests. There is no data associated to this manuscript.

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